

Performances and Activities of Urban Communities Leader Based On Sufficiency Economy Philosophy in Dusit District, Bangkok Metropolitan

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Abstract—The research studies the behaviors based on sufficiency economy philosophy at individual and community levels as well as the satisfaction of the urban community leaders by collecting data with purposive sampling technique. For in-depth interviews with 26 urban community leaders, the result shows that the urban community leaders have good knowledge and understanding about sufficiency economy philosophy. Especially in terms of money spending, they must consider the need for living and be economical. The activities in the community or society should not take advantage of the others as well as colleagues. At present, most of the urban community leaders live in sufficient way. They often spend time with public service, but many families are dealing with debt. Many communities have some political conflict and high family allowances because of living in the urban communities with rapid social and economic changes. However, there are many communities that leaders have applied their wisdom in development for their people by gathering and grouping the professionals to form activities such as making chilli sauce, textile organization, making artificial flowers to worship the sanctity. The most prominent group is the foot massage business in Wat Pracha Rabue Tham. This professional group is supported continuously by the government. One of the factors in terms of satisfaction used for evaluating community leaders is the customary administration in brotherly, interdependent way rather than using the absolute power or controlling power, but using the roles of leader to perform the activities with their people intently, determinedly and having public mind for people.

Keywords—Performance and Activities, Sufficiency Economy, Urban Communities Leader.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE 1st disseminated speech about sufficiency economy on 18th July 1974 by HM King “Country development have to be done step by step. It needs to create with the infrastructure as the supply consumption and foundation necessary of living by using Sufficiency Economy principle elements; when the basis is settled down, operation can be remained, continued and economised facilitation. This reach would be forefended miscarry and failure encountering also lead to be certainly and completely accomplishment targets.

Sufficiency Economy Philosophy leads organisations to apply their lifestyles since World Economic issued on 1997 as HM King Bhumibol given speech the significant of Sufficiency Economy to the nation,” [1]. “Sufficiency Economy based on life, consistency nation, like stakes be

fasten each dwelling and deepened on them. It is a shame they are forgotten at last” so far, Sufficiency Economy has utilized in the Tenth (2008-2012) National Economic and Social Development Plan and the Eleventh Plan (2012-2016). The majority objective is being totally restful development, although, there is complicated to classify what they are and combine to each other [2].

Fig. 1 Conceptual of Living with Happiness base on The Philosophy of Sufficiency Economy

“The middle path” is the Sufficiency Economy Philosophy continuing along with Thai social, culture and faith as display. Sufficiency Economy Philosophy will be achievement by factual doing not in abstract. The demonstrated accomplishment will be performed to next generations. Furthermore, Thais have massive faced crisis such as uncertainly economic situation and social developing state therefore, community leaders are the master of sufficiency leading likewise President Communities, Headmans, Village Chiefs, instructors and the District Chief Executives. It must be done gradually practical steps, sharing, increasing incomes, decreasing expenditures, saving and Financial Management System 30:30:30:10 [3], which is Klong Yong place, Moo 4

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Academic learning, researching and cultural transferring to communities centre is according Sufficiency Economy Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University. Moreover, leader roles are significantly carry populations out of provision by using Sufficiency Economy Principles as HM speech has over two decades in Tom Yum Kung crisis 1997, how many community behavior presently applied to Sufficiency Economy. Hence, this project will be educated that in order to encourage and develop communities themselves.

II. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

To analysis of Urban leader behaviors, community roles are by taken Sufficiency Economy Principles and sustainable Happiness leaders in Dusit District, Bangkok.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The population for this research consists of 26 communities, in total 19,847 members. There were 392 samples for Taro Yamane Formula [4]. In addition, this data has been collected by Purposive Sampling. For 26 community leaders have been appropriately interviewed times and budgets then it would be Quantitative Analysis method combined with Descriptive Statistics such Percentage, Arithmetic Mean, Standard Deviation and Inferential Statistics in order that comparing and testing data so as Independent-Sample T Test (T-Test), One-way ANOVA (F-Test) by using percentage measurement. Thereupon, Sufficiency Economy operating activities have been 5 personal levels; mean of 4.21 - 5.00(greatest);mean of 3.41 - 4.20 (great); mean of 2.61- 3.40 (intermediate); mean of 2.60 - 1.81 (low); and mean of 1.00 - 1.80 (least). In term of interviewing analysis method managed by typical significant range is made at ($\alpha = 0.9523$).

IV. RESULTS OF THE STUDY

Population in Dusit District, Bangkok had been submitted questionnaires; there were most female (63.27%), age maximum 40 years (34.69%), employee occupation (24.74%), been living in Dusit more than 31 years (36.48%), had been Sufficiency Economy training (54.85%), socio memberships (47.45%), and 26 leaders were mainly male (69.23%), maximum age 50 years (53.85%), marriage status (73.08%), Buddhism region (100%), public servant (42.31%) especially been working for the military section, education in high school/high vocational certificated (53.85%), gained incomes more than 15,000 THB (34.62%), incomes between 5,001-10,000 THB (30.77%).The analysis results will be illustrated.

TABLE I
PERSONAL ACTIVITY OPERATING LEVELS BY SUFFICIENCY ECONOMY APPLIED

Personal activity	Mean	S.D.	Level
Cost decreasing.	3.57	0.78	Great
Incomes increasing.	3.46	1.02	Great
Saving.	3.50	0.98	Great
Living.	3.95	0.72	Great
Natural resources spending and reserving.	3.99	0.70	Great
Helping each other.	3.86	0.84	Great
Total	3.72	0.70	Great

The Personal activity operating levels were high (Mean 3.72), if researcher considered to all of activities will be high level that presented bellowing

TABLE II
PERFORMED PERSONAL ACTIVITY OPERATING LEVELS BY USING SUFFICIENCY ECONOMY IN TERM OF COST DECREASING

Cost decreasing	Mean	S.D.	Level
Traveled and transported planning.	3.90	0.85	Great
Created housekeeping products.	2.93	1.38	intermediate
Fixed thing in houses by themselves.	3.66	1.04	Great
Made balance sheet every single month.	3.42	1.19	Great
Reduced unnecessary costs.	3.93	0.90	Great
Total	3.57	0.78	Great

It had presented that people would be well planned for necessary reasons but not been successful in household making.

TABLE III
ILLUSTRATED PERSONAL ACTIVITY OPERATING LEVELS BY USING SUFFICIENCY ECONOMY IN TERM OF INCREASING INCOME

Incomes increasing	Mean	S.D.	Level
Raised earnings by creating more jobs.	3.44	1.27	Great
Been participation in local communities for generating more locally profits.	3.18	1.36	intermediate
Supported locals to plant.	3.39	1.28	intermediate
Been willing to be a part of communities and intending to have more wages.	3.59	1.22	Great
Been investment and earning plans.	3.69	1.18	Great
Total	3.46	1.06	Great

The local communities prepared themselves before attending each activity also searching for more information; however, they had less associated to make community more profits.

TABLE IV
ILLUSTRATED PERSONAL ACTIVITY OPERATING LEVELS BY USING SUFFICIENCY ECONOMY IN TERM OF SAVING

Saving	Mean	S.D.	Level
Saved for the future life.	3.58	1.14	Great
Been life insurance.	3.48	1.29	Great
Been part of community saving associations.	3.27	1.43	intermediate
Been expense planed.	3.81	0.96	Great
Been saving the rest of each moth	3.39	1.24	intermediate
Total	3.50	0.98	Great

The Saving presented that population had planned for the future life in which of saving, life insurance that mean they have to save for the future costs occurring but less saving via local community saving associations.

TABLE V
ILLUSTRATED PERSONAL ACTIVITY OPERATING LEVELS BY USING SUFFICIENCY ECONOMY IN TERM OF LIVING

Living	Mean	S.D.	Level
Insisted and practiced human life along with the Dhamma principles.	4.22	0.83	Greatest
Created expenses and household cost accounting.	3.42	1.25	Great
Searched for, leaned and up to date presently situation.	3.77	1.03	Great
Persisted in Democracy roles and been reasonable living.	4.07	0.87	Great
Made a living on the right track	4.27	0.81	Greatest
Total	3.95	0.72	Great

The Living had been shown that population strictly concentrated on Dhamma then applied it to their lifestyles, been reasonable, honest and democracy but they did not control their expenses also been the least level of household accounting made.

TABLE VI
PRESENTED PERSONAL ACTIVITY OPERATING LEVELS BY USING SUFFICIENCY ECONOMY IN TERM OF NATURAL RESOURCES SPENDING AND RESERVING

Natural resources spending and reserving	Mean	S.D.	Level
Always turned electricity off when not necessary using.	4.35	0.83	Greatest
Tried to fix things in house first, then bought new one.	4.35	0.83	Greatest
Trash and garbage management.	3.90	0.97	Great
Been community participation by looking after canals, rivers and natural resources.	3.76	1.07	Great
Consumed by caring of natural environment effects	3.92	0.89	Great
Total	3.99	0.70	Great

The Natural resources spending and reserving is illustrated that population considered to natural environment effects but less attended to look after canals or rivers in their communities.

TABLE VII
PERFORMED PERSONAL ACTIVITY OPERATING LEVELS BY USING SUFFICIENCY ECONOMY IN TERM OF HELPING EACH OTHER

Helping each other	Mean	S.D.	Level
Been always community development participants.	3.71	1.11	Greatest
Paid attention to Buddhism events and given donation.	4.01	0.93	Greatest
Supported to Buddhism activities and worked with each other.	3.91	0.97	Great
Given donations to needy person.	3.91	0.98	Great
Given advising Sufficiency Economy practice and living to relatives and friends.	3.76	1.05	Great
Total	3.86	0.84	Great

The Helping each other displayed that population had kindness minds, given donations also supported Buddhism activities, more significant they would be always advised Sufficiency Economy to others but less paid attention to community development.

After 26 leaders in Dusit area interviewed, there were 8 festinating performances.

- 1) Community leaders had cost controlled, paid attention to social and local but they still had shoulder responsibilities, politic problems moreover, incomes did not balance with costs, unless the military leaders who had usual profits thus they can be cost controlled but other servants lacked of occupancy supported.
- 2) Local leaders had given the reason why it was very difficult to apply Sufficiency Economy to all due to the society, political and economic situations. They had to look for other jobs for increasing their earnings.
- 3) Community leaders had totally agreed how to control living cost so they planted and cooked themselves also trained the leaders families to be representative for all in term of saving infrastructures usage and decreasing waste costs.

- 4) Local leaders had created various activities to gain more benefits for all such as fresh markets, massaging and recycle processing, in addition, provided career training to raise their turnover up.
- 5) Leaders had 3 Cost planning systems like 1. Fixed-term deposits, 2. Saving deposits and 3. The rest of household expenditures and had taught their under caring persons [5]. Furthermore, leaders had taken community saving co-operatives or privacy operation for saving their funds.
- 6) Partial leaders had some problem to adjust their life styles with Sufficiency Economy on the other hand, they always concerned how to have the worth living, treated their members to have not only earnings but also cost planning.
- 7) Leaders had paid attention to plant, turned off electricity when away, kept local villages clean especially in Wat Noi Noppakun had effective Microorganisms operation for helping community cleaned.
- 8) Leaders had always looked after their families, consulted and taken part in locals other than, they searched for more organisations to encourage persons who have no chance, so as to all community membership have to forgive each other and support and sharing each other eventually.

Sufficiency Economy adapted to development behaviour dimension in localisation found that Rabuetham massaging group, located on Wat Pracha Rabuetham, Dusit District, Bangkok was the best of all participants, which they had every single month meeting for leaders, supported who lacked of opportunities also the Dusit District Administration centre offered them more activities[6]. There have generated the connection to each other in and out locally, it was not only link economic, social, natural environment but also local wisdom appropriated. Moreover, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University has cooperated with various urban communities in which of Academic participation, financial supported to villages, and especially it was on Children day, many firms were wailings to support. Other more, when firing and flooding occurred they would have suddenly contacted to relevant segments in Dusit location also helped from the military likewise, created events which objectives to increase the relationship between cities such Sport day, Big cleaning day, been volunteers looked after the city and exchange information to others. Furthermore, there had an organization wanted to take part in Wat Ranuetham village in order to settle Nursing care college as same as Kuekarun nursing care college. Suwaree Yodchim [7] reported that whole pleasure of leaders have been working, letting membership admired along with Sufficiency Economy principles. Majority leader job descriptions were giving advice, helping to members for instance, they have plenty of lands so leaders would recommend to grow and plant some fruits or vegetables for reducing consumption costs then they provided membership to make balance sheet accounting in order that realised how much they had spent. Because of globalization, it is quickly changed, uncertain, high cost of living, hence, they have to save it as much as they can and be taken Sufficiency Economy philosophy for all persons [8].

Practising factors along Sufficiency Economy principles in

Dusit area:

- 1) Been Sufficiency Economy participation training, shown that people who had ever taken part in Sufficiency Economy practicing were different from one who had never done it before, with typical significant range is made at 0.05. The persons who had been trained, they would be affective done more activities than never.
- 2) Been socio membership, found that people who had been socio members were differed from who never done in term of practicing along with Sufficiency Economy with typical significant range is 0.05. The persons who are social members able to do employment and household events more than who never done.

V. CONCLUSION

Urban leaders have applied to all Sufficiency Economy activities with the maximum to the minimum levels accordingly 1. Using and reserving natural environment (average 3.99) 2. Living (average 3.95) 3. Helping each other (average 3.86) 4. Decreasing cost (average 3.57) 5. Saving (average 3.50) 6. Increasing incomes (average 3.46) especially, Living section has the most level of the right and honest working, not over-investment (average 4.27) and Dhamma practicing (average 4.22) including to using and spending natural environment has the maximum level, in operation level which saving electricity when not necessary (average 4.35). However, city living, leaders have to be a great representative of Sufficiency Economy and well practicing all the time then life will be cheerfulness.

VI. DISCUSSION

Sufficiency Economy practicing shown that leaders always taken in using and reserving natural resources (average 3.99) the highest average especially turned off the electricity when away from homes or unnecessary (average 4.35) due to in downtown has various used the energy hence, cost of them will getting high. Moreover, they paid attention to be less using electricity. For example; the military in Battalion 9 Security Centre, Royal Thai Armed Forces Head Quarters have been applicable Sufficiency Economy to their life styles. They utilised electricity with saving guaranteed, taken household cost control [9]. More and more, all of leaders and members lacked of association making, social group and jobs creation which the lowest average (3.18) due to most of them have main occupations, they have no time to share in communities also the basis of careers of this area were hiring with maximum earnings 10,000 THB and more essential happened that population have been living here over 30 years thus they known how to adopt life with global society, it was not different to Sufficiency Economy practising. Most of their times spent on raise incomes so it no wonder why they have little consumption times. For fixing things, they would try to fix first then get new one if they cannot. While, balancing sheet accounting, they have not usually done because of they paid attention to gain more wages then less looked after making balance sheet each month. As the similar result of

relationship between understanding Sufficiency Economy and household accounting recorded, the research as in Tombon Nong Prai, Muang District, Udonthani Province displayed that total household accountant recording was moderated level[10].

VII. SUGGESTIONS

Leaders have to always advise and discuss about technology using, they should get it appropriated with income, worth but the problem is members used technology over their budgets and needed not only mobile phone but also high cost of laptops or notebooks. Moreover, they have to make and create products for usage in household such as mop or dish cleaning gel also more attend to plant vegetable themselves, saving and create more wages to self and families. Furthermore, they have to be a part of communities where they live in order to increase more jobs by joining community household groups or housewife groups or other groups settled.

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